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List of abbreviations

ARIMA	A uto r egression i ntegrated m oving a verage
DACF	D ay- a head c ongestion f orecast
DOW	D escription o f w ork
DSO	D istribution s ystem o perator
cdf	C umulative d istribution f unction
cpdf	C onditional p robability d ensity f unction
CKDE	C onditional K DE
ecdf	E mpirical c umulative d istribution f unction
IC	I ntra-day c ycle
MC	M onte C arlo
MISE	M ean i ntegrated s quared e rror
KDE	K ernel d ensity e stimation
LF	L oad f orecasting
LT	L ong- t erm
NWP	N umeric w eather p rediction
pdf	P robability d ensity f unction
PV	P hotovoltaic
RMSE	R oot- m ean- s quare e rror
ST	S hort t erm
TSO	T ransmission s ystem o perator
VST	V ery s hort- t erm

1 Introduction

1.1 Outline and Framework of this Deliverable

This deliverable is a report of the work done in the framework of the Umbrella project in Task 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 of Work Package 2 as defined in the description of work (DOW) of the Umbrella project [1]. The individual titles of the tasks according to the DOW [[1], pp. 7-8] are:

1. Integrating uncertainty in renewable power forecasts,
2. Integrating uncertainty in short-term trading,
3. Integrating uncertainty in load forecasts and power plant outages.

In the DOW [[1], p. 9] the contents of the Deliverable 2.1 are outlined as follows:

Report on uncertainty modeling:

1. Report of stochastic structures of renewable infeed, load forecast and power plant outages as well as proposal of instruments to describe them,
2. Analysis of intraday rescheduling and a subsequent proposal for statistical description,
3. Report of suitable descriptions of the associated uncertainties in view of providing a consistent overall system state description.

Based on the DOW, this report is structured as follows. Chapter 1 gives some background information. Chapter 2 describes the outcome of task 2.1, namely the analysis and modeling of the uncertainty of wind and solar power infeed, load forecasting as well as power plant outages. Chapter 3 focuses on uncertainties resulting from intraday trading. The uncertainty of load forecasting and power plant outages is outlined in chapter 4. The model presented in chapter 3 requires methods that are outlined in chapter 2 and 4. Subsequently, chapter 5 combines the results from the uncertainty analysis in order to derive an interface that allows for using the uncertainties within the description of the overall system states. The deliverable concludes in chapter 6.

This deliverable was compiled under the lead of the University Duisburg-Essen. Further participants were Graz University of Technology (lead of section 4.1) and RWTH Aachen (lead of section 4.2).

1.2 Background

The energy landscape of Europe has been altered heavily in recent years. Besides the liberalization of the electricity market, the climate policy of the European Union (EU) that also defines targets for the electricity generation provided by renewable energy sources (RES) has important implications for the operation of the European transmission grid. Uncertainties on the demand side, namely load forecasting uncertainties, are well-known and under control for years. On the supply side, the uncertainty of power plant outages

was the major concern transmission system operators (TSOs) had to face for many years. Nowadays, we witness a strong shift in the power system due to growing energy supplies from RESs. This has not only consequences on the supply side, but also on the demand side, because many wind and solar farms feed in subordinate grids, which is not directly observable by the TSOs. Especially the intermittent nature of wind requires methods to anticipate changes of wind and, thus, wind power production. However, no forecast is perfect. In order to cope with the forecast error, it is necessary to know the possible magnitude of under- or overestimations and its probability, so that TSOs are enabled to identify potential risks for a secure operation of their respective control area early and start the necessary actions to prevent such system states. This is one of the major objectives of this work package.

Besides the forecast error, the increasing amount of RESs also has an impact on intraday trades and, hence, on the secure operation of the grid. If the energy output of wind or solar power farms deviates from the expected output, conventional power plants have to adjust their power output accordingly. In as far as the decision of changing the power plant's output is driven by purely commercial factors, the adjustment of the conventional power plants might jeopardize the system even more. To predict the mentioned adjustments and the resulting changes of power flows as well as their uncertainty is also a major contribution of work package 2.

Most of the mentioned processes are more or less easy to predict individually. However, TSOs have limited information on the detail of these processes, but can only observe an aggregation of them. This makes the collection of data and its use more difficult. Figure 1 illustrates this situation graphically.

Having analyzed all the main uncertainties and being able to forecast them would lead to an amount of data and information that is hard to handle for TSOs. Thus, the uncertainties and especially the correlation between uncertainties at different sites in the grid have to be translated in a standard that provides meaningful and quick decision guidance for TSOs. How to achieve a descriptive overall system state description is also part of the deliverable at hand.

Figure 1: Obervable and non-obersvable influence factors

2 Modeling the uncertainty of renewable power forecasts

This chapter is split into three sections. Section 2.1 states some general concepts. Section 2.2 and 2.3 explain the modeling of wind and solar power forecast uncertainty. Thereby, the origin of the problem is outlined, a short review on probabilistic methods for the very case is given, the methodology is elaborated and, at the end, results are described.

2.1 Forecasting uncertainty

Before we go into detail, it should be stated which type of statistical interval is required for the problem at hand. In general, three statistical intervals can be distinguished, namely confidence intervals, statistical tolerance intervals (or just tolerance intervals) and prediction intervals [2]. Confidence intervals assess the range of a parameter of the sampled population, e.g. the mean. Tolerance intervals make a statement about a predefined proportion of the sampled population. Thus, confidence intervals and tolerance intervals are not suitable for probabilistic forecasting of renewable energy feed-ins. Prediction intervals estimate the range of future observations given a certain sample, what makes them predestined for probabilistic forecasting.

As will be shown later, some methods are able to provide the entire probability density function (pdf) of future observations. Hence, instead of generating just one prediction interval with a given probability, several prediction intervals can be obtained easily from the pdf.

2.2 Wind power forecast uncertainty

2.2.1 Deterministic wind power forecasting

Nowadays, two well-known approaches to predict wind power exist, namely the physical and the statistical approach. They can be based upon Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models, which are made available through national meteorological services and provide the most important meteorological parameters [3].

The most straightforward way to convert weather predictions into wind power predictions is the physical approach [3]. Thereby, wind speed predictions from a NWP model must be transformed to the hub height of the wind turbine and subsequently converted with the respective power curve [4]. The power curve of a wind generator defines the relationship between the wind speed at rotor level and the resulting electric power. Additionally, special refinements to consider local characteristics and wind farm effects, e.g. shadowing effects, are taken into account. This is usually followed by a regional upscaling to produce predictions for larger areas without the need to assess each wind turbine. However, the

main drawbacks of the physical approach are the necessary detailed information and the effort required to set up the forecasting system [3].

The statistical approach uses historical data and mostly additional explanatory variables to predict wind power [5]. Such models can also be combined with the physical approach. Within the same group but sometimes considered as an extra group are methods from the field of artificial intelligence such as artificial neural networks (ANNs), support vector machines and nearest neighbour search. They require a large data set to learn the relationship between weather forecasts and the power output [3].

What makes wind power forecasting so difficult is the non-linear (cubic) relationship between wind speed and wind power, which leads to large wind power forecast errors when the wind speed forecast error is still small.

More detailed information about the vast range of wind power forecast models has been compiled by [6].

2.2.2 Probabilistic wind power forecasting

In addition to the aforementioned point forecasts, probability forecasts have become state-of-the-art in nowadays wind prediction tools [6]. When distinguishing between the inputs of a model, three approaches exist to estimate the uncertainty of wind power predictions [7]. Firstly, the point forecasts of a NWP model can be used as an input of a probabilistic model that estimates the forecasting uncertainty. Secondly, ensemble predictions from a NWP model can be transformed into an ensemble wind power prediction that has to be post-processed in order to obtain probabilistic wind power forecasts. The third approach uses wind power point predictions directly and sometimes also the output of the NWP model as input of a probabilistic wind power model [7].

Moreover, depending on how the uncertainty is finally computed, two different approaches exist. Firstly, the prediction interval of the predicted wind power can be derived directly from the wind power prediction (direct approach [8]). Secondly, a wider range of models focuses on the probability distribution of the forecast error conditional on the predicted wind power and adds the expected error distribution to the wind power prediction (prediction error approach [8]).

Furthermore, the literature on probabilistic wind power forecasting can be divided into a branch that applies parametric methods and a non-parametric branch. The latter is widely preferred due to the statistical properties of the wind power forecast error [5] and the inherent and mostly inaccurate assumptions of the parametric approaches.

One of the first non-parametric methods uses quantile regression with additional explanatory variables [9]. Thereby, each quantile requires an extra model, which would lead to 19 models if it is intended to model the entire prediction interval in 0.05 quantile steps [5]. A part from that, [9] states that the individual modelling of each quantile, could result in overlapping quantiles. This is why, [5] as well as [10] prefer an empirical distribution obtained with a fuzzy inference model. Thereby, the error sample is divided into different non-overlapping subsets depending on the forecast conditions. Each of these

subsets has its own empirical distribution, which are then joined using a fuzzy logic. In various applications of the model ([11], [12]), the subsets have been chosen according to the power curve in order to account for its non-linearity and to incorporate different conditions when there exists a cut-off risk, i.e. when the wind generator has to be switched off due to equipment damaging wind speeds. Although [5] introduces two approaches to estimate the weight for the combination of the single empirical distributions, namely the linear opinion pool and the adapted re-sampling method, only the last one has been applied by [11] as well as [12], because it is superior to the aforementioned approach [10]. Strictly speaking, [5] creates a predictive interval instead of a generic pdf [8], but by creating multiple predictive intervals one could produce a (empirical) pdf. However, deriving a continuous pdf could yield an additional benefit for wind farm operators or TSOs. [13] emphasize that the pdf provides the user with all necessary information, describes the random variable completely, and still gives the possibility to generate other desired statistical parameters out of it. This leads to another approach to create probabilistic forecasts, namely the kernel density estimation (KDE).

KDE provides a continuous pdf by assigning sample values to a certain point in the pdf by its “contribution”, which is weighted by a prior chosen kernel function [14]. In order to incorporate explanatory variables, [8] and [13] have chosen a conditional pdf. Obstacles to overcome are inter alia a proper correction of the boundary effect [15] and the appropriate selection of the kernel function. Whereas [8] initiated the usage of KDE in wind power forecasting, [13] present a time-adaptive approach that copes with the aforementioned obstacles. Thereby, [13] utilize a copula to model the dependence between the explanatory variables and wind power.

In addition, recent publications focus on ensemble forecasting [16]. Ensemble forecasts are produced with the help of NWP models by creating different scenarios. This can be achieved by changing the initial conditions, which is especially useful when the atmospheric situation is unstable [11]. Thereby, the different outcomes of the NWP model runs provide the pdf of the predicted wind power [17].

Unfortunately, the comparison of the various approaches is not standardized and requires exactly the same data to obtain reliable results [18]. Some guidelines for the comparison of point predictions have been developed by [19]. Furthermore, [12] introduced an evaluation framework in order to assess the quality of probabilistic forecasts.

2.2.3 Required properties of probabilistic wind power forecasts for TSOs

Knowing the various approaches mentioned above, it is not an easy task to pick a method that fulfills all the TSO’s needs. Therefore, we intend to take a closer look at the required properties of probabilistic wind power forecasts for TSOs in this paragraph.

2.2.3.1 Temporal resolution and consideration of the look-ahead time

The temporal resolution of the probabilistic forecast is dictated by operational issues. Thus, an hourly resolution that goes along with the Day-Ahead Congestion Forecast

(DACF) process should be the minimum requirement. A quarter-hourly resolution captures the intermittent nature of wind far better and is ideal for comparisons with Snapshots. In the end, TSOs have to decide and might even consider both resolutions.

As mentioned earlier, the uncertainty of deterministic forecasts increases with an increasing look-ahead time [5]. Thus, a different estimator should be used for each look-ahead time in order to regard this property.

2.2.3.2 Spatial resolution

Especially with an increasing installed wind power capacity, the spatial resolution ought to increase. Thus, estimating a different uncertainty distribution for each grid node is ideal. TSOs with less installed wind power capacity could consider starting with a lower resolution such as postal code area and moving to a grid node level when the installed capacity increases further. However, the uncertainty of wind power infeeds is used as an input for load flow calculations, so that a grid node resolution becomes inevitable.

2.2.3.3 Conditional properties

As outlined in [5], the uncertainty of wind power forecasts is higher when the point forecast is medium-high and generally lower when the point forecast is low or high. This particularity has to be exploited by the uncertainty forecasting tool by implementing an estimator which is conditional on the point forecast.

2.2.3.4 Information content

It has been already emphasized that only the probability distribution function provides the user with the full information about the forecast error. Hence, it is desirable to estimate the entire pdf and cpdf, respectively.

2.2.4 Methodology

The selection of an adequate method is restricted by the data availability and the daily grid operation processes, i.e. operational planning and real-time operation. TSOs do not possess NWP data for a deep analysis. However, deterministic wind power forecasts can be purchased from service providers in a wide range of detail. In addition, the prediction method should be easy to apply. Hence, a prediction error approach that takes as input only point predictions and measurements is favorable. The wind power forecast error should be observable for each grid node i ($i = 1, \dots, I$).

For a certain forecast start time t and look-ahead time k the wind power forecast error is defined as:

$$E_{t+k,i} = \hat{P}_{t+k,i} - P_{t+k,i}$$

where $P_{t+k,i}$ is the measured and $\hat{P}_{t+k,i}$ the forecasted wind power feed-in at the grid node i with $\hat{P}_{t+k,i} \in [0,1]$. Due to the aforementioned conditional property $\hat{P}_{t+k,i} = 0$ leads to $E_{t+k,i} \in [-1,0]$ and $\hat{P}_{t+k,i} = 1$ to $E_{t+k,i} \in [0,1]$.

2.2.4.1 Estimation of the forecast error's conditional probability for each grid node

The cpdf that has to be estimated is $f_{E_{t+k,i}}(e_{t+k,i} | \hat{P}_{t+k,i} = \hat{p}_{t+k,i})$. We denote the estimate as $\hat{f}_{E_{k,i}}(e | \hat{P} = \hat{p})$. If the point forecast is issued always at the same time and for the same forecast horizon, the estimate becomes independent of t .

Because only kernel density estimators are capable of estimating the entire pdf and cpdf, respectively, a kernel density estimator is applied. Besides the quantile-copula approach [20], the widely-used Nadaraya-Watson estimator has the advantage of being easy to apply and intuitive. The Nadaraya-Watson estimator has also performed well compared to state-of-the-art methods [21]. In our case, the Nadaraya-Watson estimator can be rewritten as:

$$\hat{f}_{E_{k,i}}(e | \hat{P} = \hat{p}) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^J K_{e_{k,i}/h_{e_{k,i}}+1, (1-e_{k,i})/h_{e_{k,i}}+1}(e_{k,i,j}) \cdot K_{\hat{p}_{k,i}/h_{\hat{p}_{k,i}}+1, (1-\hat{p}_{k,i})/h_{\hat{p}_{k,i}}+1}(\hat{p}_{k,i,j})}{\sum_{j=1}^J K_{\hat{p}_{k,i}/h_{\hat{p}_{k,i}}+1, (1-\hat{p}_{k,i})/h_{\hat{p}_{k,i}}+1}(\hat{p}_{k,i,j})}$$

where K is a first-beta kernel estimator as in [22]. The main advantage of the beta kernels by [22] is that they are free of boundary bias and achieve the optimal rate of convergence for the mean integrated squared error (MISE). The first-beta kernel estimator has performed better than the second-beta kernel when applied to wind speed and power [23]. Moreover, the forecast error $e_{k,i}$ has to be transformed beforehand, because the support of the beta kernel is $[0,1]$. This is achieved by shifting all values so that they are greater than or equal to zero $e_{k,i}^{trans} = e_{k,i} + |\min\{e_{k,i}\}|, \forall i \in I$ and by normalizing the outcome with the greatest value $e_{k,i}^{trans} = \frac{e_{k,i}^{trans}}{\max\{e_{k,i}^{trans}\}}, \forall i \in I$. Least squares cross-validation is used to select the smoothing parameters $h_{e_{k,i}}, h_{\hat{p}_{k,i}}$ [14]. Please note that the selection of the smoothing parameters should be done separately for each pdf due to deviating distributions.

How to modify the described estimator to a time-adaptive version is outlined in [13] and [24].

2.2.4.2 Estimation of the spatial dependences between the forecast error of grid nodes

In order to simulate forecast errors while taking spatial dependences into account, a copula outperforms other dependence measurers because it models the dependence structure over the whole domain differently. A copula defines the relationship between a joint distribution function and its marginal distribution functions [25]. Thus, a copula also provides the TSO with information on the wind power uncertainty of larger areas or the entire control area.

For the sake of simplicity, a Gaussian copula is used. Before the estimation of the copula parameter, the conditional pdfs of the forecast error have to be transformed into Gaussian

distributed random variables. This is implemented as in [26] except of an extra step that has to be undertaken in order to transform the conditional pdfs into unconditional cumulative distribution functions (cdf). The subsequent steps state the transformation:

1. Compute the ccdf of the forecast error by applying the trapezoidal rule for numerical integration: $\hat{F}_{E_{k,i}}(e | \hat{P} = \hat{p}) = \int_{-\infty}^e \hat{f}_{E_{k,i}}(u | \hat{P} = \hat{p}) du$,
2. Run through the historical data set of $e_{t+k,i}$ as well as $\hat{p}_{t+k,i}$ and compute the estimates of the cpdf in order to obtain an empirical cdf denoted as $\hat{F}_{e_{k,i}}$.

Subsequently, the same transformation as in [26] can be used in order to obtain Gaussian distributed random variables:

$$\hat{F}_{e_{k,i}} = U_{k,i} \Leftrightarrow \Phi^{-1}(U_{k,i}) = X_{k,i}.$$

Later, by applying the same transformation backwards ($\Phi(X_{k,i}) = U_{k,i} \Leftrightarrow \hat{F}_{e_{k,i}}^{-1}$) in combination with the respective point prediction, the pdf of the forecast error can be simulated.

In our case, the Gaussian Copula for I grid nodes is:

$$C_k(\hat{F}_{e_{k,1}}, \hat{F}_{e_{k,2}}, \dots, \hat{F}_{e_{k,I}}; \rho) = \Phi_{\rho}(X_{k,1}, X_{k,2}, \dots, X_{k,I})$$

where Φ_{ρ} is a standard I-variate normal distribution and the ρ correlation matrix. The Canonical Likelihood method is used in order to estimate ρ .

2.2.5 Wind power data

Although the DoW states that “data for the analysis including RES infeeds are provided by TSO project partners at an appropriate level of detail” [1, p. 7], this kind of data is not integrated in the TSOs’ operational processes and, thus, not yet available. In order to pursue the analysis a data test set (includes so far only Germany) has been generated, which is described subsequently. This will also help to identify in a later stage of the project which kind of data is necessary for TSOs.

2.2.5.1 Wind farms

The data test set includes the modeling of 5773 wind farms in Germany, which account for more than 27 GW of installed capacity¹. Besides the rated power, geographic position data is also available. The exact power curve was unavailable for about 40 % of the wind farms. In order to resolve this, we generated ten power curve classes based on the rated power with three typical representatives in each group. Then, a wind farm with an unknown power curve was assigned randomly to one representative in its power class. Because the

¹ For more information please see <http://www.thewindpower.net>.

power curve is normalized with the rated power, all wind farms with unknown power curves keep their rated power.

2.2.5.2 *Wind power measurements*

Wind power measurements are modeled with wind speeds at each site and the power curve. The wind speed measurements are provided by the German Meteorological Service². They have been interpolated to the wind farm sites using linear inverse distance weighting and, in a second step, to the hub height of the wind farms using the roughness length. Because the wind speeds lose accuracy due to the interpolation and the wind power curves are stochastic [24], the modeled power measurements are somewhat inaccurate. That is why we refer to them as pseudo wind power measurements.

2.2.5.3 *Wind power forecasts*

State-of-the-art artificial intelligence techniques [27] have been applied in order to obtain wind power forecasts. The advantage is that these approaches require only wind speed and direction forecasts as input, but also perform satisfactorily. Therefore, output from a European NWP model called COSMO-EU³ has been used. COSMO-EU provides hourly wind speed and direction forecasts for a 7x7 km grid over Europe. The forecasting horizon has been chosen to coincide with one day. The artificial neural networks have been trained with data from the whole year of 2010 and then retrained biannually until the end of 2012. The aforementioned pseudo wind power measurements were used for calibration.

2.2.5.4 *Transmission grid*

In order to obtain distributions for each grid node, information about the situation in underlying grids is necessary because most wind farms are not connected to the transmission grid, but to underlying voltage levels. Because this information is not available yet, we assume that a wind farm feeds in the closest transmission grid node. There is also a scenario where a wind farm feeds in the three closest grid nodes weighted by the inverse distance to them. Until now, no judgment on the performance of the assumptions is possible, but will be at a later stage of the project.

It should be mentioned that there are other factors that influence the actual uncertainty of wind power forecasting. Firstly, wind farms that are in maintenance mode will lead to an overestimation of the uncertainty, which is from a security point of view uncritical. Secondly, switching operations in underlying grids could lead to unexpected deviations from the point forecast at certain grid nodes. Unfortunately, this can only be observed and, thus, incorporated in the uncertainty estimation when real data becomes available.

² For more information please see <http://www.dwd.de>.

³ For more information please see <http://www.dwd.de>.

2.2.6 Results

Exemplary results on the estimation results are given in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Figure 2 shows the forecast intervals for a selected grid node with high wind infeed in Northern Germany (about 196 MW installed wind power capacity). The quantiles of the forecast distribution are plotted over the prediction horizon. Against first intuition, the uncertainty bandwidth does not increase with increasing forecast horizon in that particular case. The reason is that for the more distant time steps the expected infeed is lower and therefore the downwards deviations are limited. A further reason is that forecast deviations in wind speed do not translate into as high deviations in wind power since the non-linear power curve of the wind turbines has a lower slope at these wind speed levels.

Figure 3 shows the corresponding correlation between the computed forecast errors in the 29 grid nodes of an undertaken case study. More precisely it is the resulting correlation matrix after the Gaussian copula has been applied. The results are given in the upper part for the forecast horizon of one hour, in the lower part for the forecast horizon of six hours. It becomes obvious that the dependence structure changes with the forecast horizon, what motivates different copulas for different look-ahead times. The nodes are sorted by increasing distance from a reference node. Obviously the correlation between the forecast errors in the close vicinity of the reference node is very high, whereas the correlation to more distant grid nodes declines rapidly. This is true almost independently of the forecast horizon.

Figure 2: Exemplary results of wind power forecast distributions for a selected grid node as a function of the forecast interval

Figure 3: Exemplary results on correlation matrix between different grid nodes

2.2.7 First simulations

The obtained estimation results have been used to perform first simulation runs – as will be then performed with the prototype tool. Exemplary results are shown in Figure 4 including a distribution with actual forecast error distributions. Obviously the distribution of the actual forecast errors is rather similar to the simulated ones even if the simulations have a less pronounced peak than the actual observations.

Figure 4: Exemplary results on simulated forecast error distributions and comparison with the actual observations

2.3 Solar power forecast uncertainty

2.3.1 Deterministic solar power forecasting

Whereas in wind power forecasting the relationship between the major influencing meteorological parameter (wind speed) and the parameter of interest (wind power) is non-linear, the relationship between global irradiance and solar power is almost linear [28]. Thus, the problem of forecasting solar power becomes the problem of forecasting global irradiance.

The choice of a forecasting method depends heavily on the prediction horizon. Very short-term models use sky images in order to predict the movement of clouds and, thus, the irradiance. For forecast horizons of up to six hours, satellite images in combination with NWP models provide good results [28]. Models that allow predicting solar power up to three days take normally only NWPs as input [29]. PV system characteristics such as the tilt of the panels are taken into account as well.

Another particularity in solar power forecasting is that the prediction accuracy depends heavily on the climatic conditions in the very area. For example, the relative root-mean-square error (RMSE) for a day-ahead forecast in a central European region is at least 20 percentage points higher than in Spain [30]. Thus, the uncertainty assessment should take this property in account.

2.3.2 Probabilistic solar power forecasting

In contrast to wind power forecasting, the amount of literature that focuses on probabilistic solar power forecasting is quite limited. [28] outlines the potential of quantile regression briefly. Quantile regression has also been applied in wind power forecasting. [29] suggest a parametric approach that assumes a normal distribution. Thereby, the clear sky index and the solar zenith angle are used to select the standard deviation for this very time step. When the method is applied to an ensemble of solar power plants (regional forecast), an error reduction factor is utilized. Consequently, the quality of the probabilistic power forecast depends also on the reduction factor.

1.1.1 Required properties of probabilistic solar power forecasts for TSOs

The integration of solar power forecasts and their uncertainty into operational processes demands the same requirements as probabilistic wind power forecasts, which are described in section 2.2.3.

2.3.3 Methodology

Although the linear relationship between global irradiance and solar power might suggest a parametric approach, it is not practical for TSOs, because it requires situation-dependent input. In addition, there is little knowledge about how aggregated errors behave in terms of skewness and kurtosis, and how this is changing from region to region. That is why we apply the same approach as for wind power, which is outlined in section 2.2.4.

3 Modeling the uncertainty of short-term trading

3.1 Drivers for short-term trading

Fundamental changes on the supply or the demand side are a major driver for short-term trading. Their impact will be discussed in section 3.1.1. Other drivers for short-term trading are analyzed in section 3.1.2.

3.1.1 Changes in supply and demand

Basically, changes on the supply side may be subdivided as follows:

- Forecast updates for intermittent renewables production
 - Wind
 - Solar
- Unforeseen production changes for conventional power plants
 - Outages
 - Others

Whereas forecast errors may both increase and decrease the power supply in a certain region, outages will only reduce the supply side. Other production changes for conventional plants may include reconnection after some outage which had not been scheduled on the day-ahead market.

At unchanged demand, any change in supply has to be compensated by a change in opposite direction in the operation of another unit – e.g. the outage of a lignite plant may be compensated by additional production in a gas fired plant. This shift in production gives rise to intraday trade – be it between different market participants or be it just within the different sites of one company.

Similarly also deviations on the demand side may give rise to intraday trade. Here there is mostly one driver:

- Forecast updates for load

These may again be upwards or downwards, inducing a parallel adjustment in controllable production. They will typically be carried out by the balancing area responsible which are the suppliers in this case, not the TSOs. Unless the load and production adjustment occurs in the same grid node, it will result in some changed grid flows.

One may note that deviations between the DACF and the Snapshot do not only include forecast updates leading to intraday trade but also those deviations which are not settled intraday but are compensated via the use of reserve or regulating power. Again this induces changes in the intraday distribution of supply and demand and subsequently also of the load flows. And it may be described by similar approaches although in the detail some differences should be preferably taken into account.

3.1.2 Other drivers

Besides fundamental factors, also other effects may explain part of the intraday trading observed. At least the timing and the frequency of trading may be explained also by non-fundamental factors such as the availability of traders [31]. It is however unclear to what extent such factors affect actually the fundamental production and consumption patterns in the electricity market. Moreover they are rather difficult to quantify when it comes to assessing their impact on physical load flows. Therefore these drivers are not considered further subsequently.

3.2 Modeling short-term trading

The basic idea for modeling the impact of short-term trading on the power plant dispatch is to consider a modified version of a merit order model. The merit order model orders the available generation capacities by increasing marginal generation costs. The actual production pattern and price are then determined by determining the intersection between the supply curve and the current demand (cf. Figure 5).

For modeling the intraday market it is crucial to include in the merit order only those capacities that can flexibly react to a demand – supply imbalance. For example for a base load lignite or nuclear plant, typically only the difference between the maximum output and the minimum stable operation limit can be used in the intraday trading. Otherwise significant start-up costs may be incurred.

Figure 5: Basic merit-order model to analyse the impact of intraday trading

A further difference to the conventional merit order is that the focus is on horizontal shifts in either the supply or the demand side (cf. Figure 5). Therefore it is crucial to get as inputs the simulated distributions of forecast errors for wind, solar and load as well as simulated power plant outages. These have to be aggregated at a national level to determine the induced shift in the supply-demand balance and the corresponding changes in the dispatch of controllable generation units.

This approach has been implemented as a MATLAB code and extensive checks on the database to be used and the results obtained have been carried out.

3.3 Results

The results obtained so far indicate that the quality of the power plant representation is crucial for success. If the TSOs do not have detailed information on the existing power plants, e.g. because they feed into lower voltage levels, then this may strongly impede the results of the intraday trading modeling.

In order to reduce the uncertainty bandwidth it is therefore important that the TSOs organize their processes as effectively as possible to make use of all available information (e.g. production schedules of power plants). Also estimates of variable costs need to be kept up to date in order to assure the validity of the approach.

A general difficulty is that parts of the merit order are rather flat in many European countries. Then it is difficult to estimate correctly which power plant will actually be used first in the merit order. The deterministic approach developed here is then too narrow. It could be complemented by some stochastic estimate of the variable costs uncertainty.

4 Modeling the uncertainty of load forecasts and power plant outages

4.1 Load forecast uncertainty

Load forecasting is an important topic since the beginning of interconnected grids and the transmission of electricity, which has led to a nearly inexhaustible amount of literature with various key aspects. Thus, diverse applications, approaches and combinations of approaches can be found in literature. In the following sub-chapter the literature survey summarises the most common methods in forecasting and gives an overview about their advantages and disadvantages. Subsequently the methods used by the TSOs whose grid area data were investigated are explained in detail. In the special case of data delivered by TSOs there is only a small amount of “load-only” nodes, so the other nodal power time series combine a mixture of underlying generation in the grid of distribution system operators (DSOs) in the form of centralised as well as dispersed in-feeds like photovoltaic, small hydro power plants, single wind turbines, non-high voltage connected wind parks, as well as small scale combined heat and power and so on. So the characteristics of the high voltage vertical grid loads consist not only of a demand part but also of a generative one, which cannot always be identified as such.

4.1.1 Load Forecasting Methods

Given the long-time load behaviour has been researched, numerous forecasting methods originated out of this work. Depending on the time series characteristics like the existence of a trend, the type of trend, seasonality (daily, weekly, ...), influence parameters like the weather, special days as well as structural shifts in energy system structure (e.g. the upcoming of dispersed generation and the ability of power on demand side management) have been taken into account.

Univariate and Multivariate Models

Univariate models analyse a single variable such as the load. Multivariate models are more sophisticated and take external parameters (like weather data or special days as well as holidays) into account. Most papers suggest that the influence of external factors does not affect the accuracy of the calculation's results in terms of VSTLF and the near future part of STLF. This leads to (h-1) models without an implementation of these external factors performing better for short term forecasts than weather based multivariate models to a lead time of 5 hours, because the meteorological parameters do not change fast over time.

Additive- and Multiplicative Models

There are generally two mathematical different categories in forecasting methods namely the additive models (sum of a number of components) and the multiplicative models (product of a number of components) [32].

$$L = L_n + L_w + L_s + L_r$$

There L is the total predicted load, L_n is the normal part of the load according to the standardised profile of the considered day, L_w implements the weather dependent share of the load, L_s is a term for special events leading to a deviation of the usual load structure and L_r represents a random term also called noise.

$$L = L_n \cdot F_w \cdot F_s \cdot F_r$$

The load parameters again represent the above mentioned behaviour but as factors instead of summative terms. Also factors like electricity pricing (simple market modelling) and the growth (trend) of the load can be integrated into the formula.

Weather Dependency

Basically the load's behaviour depends on many factors. The most influential one is the temperature, but also the time, or better the seasonality like winter-summer, day-night, weekday-weekend, vacation and special days, as well as the degree of cloud covering, the wind speed, the humidity and the electricity price affect the load pattern. The economic trend influences the future, to be forecasted load pattern, too. Also a term of randomness takes part of the load's behaviour like large customers shutting down, or powering up causing sudden load changes as well as non-predictable natural and civil events. Most of the load prediction models are univariate in respect to the day. Advanced models also take the effects on the energy demand caused by weather changes into account. The temperature is in general a slow changing value and there is also a delay caused by heat storages. It affects directly the customer's energy demand through the use of heating or cooling appliances. The impact of humidity changes is very similar to those of the temperature. A higher humidity leads to an increase in energy demand because of people's subjective perception. This relationship is represented by the thermal-humidity-index describing the effect of heat discomfort. In countries with a huge amount of electrical powered heatings the weather factors play a more important role in load forecasting than in conventional heated areas. In these areas the influence of the wind on the load has to be considered because of its cooling effect underlying the effect of inertia [33]. Inertia leads to a shift in time and so a cold or windy day does not directly cause an increase in energy demand because buildings have a thermal time constant. The influence of wind on the subjective climate perception is described by the wind-chill-factor indicating the presence of cold stress. Because the load is closely connected to the parameters of the weather, the weather forecast quality influences directly the quality of the load forecast. The impact of a bad temperature or wind prediction can be determined by forecasting the load on the basis of the observed weather using historical meteorological data and load data for verification purposes. So the direct influence of a climate change or a prediction inaccuracy can be expressed as an amount of power.

4.1.1.1 *Naive Approaches*

In general, it can be said that sophisticated prediction approaches lead to better results and so to smaller residuals than naive ones but in terms of very short term forecasting simple univariate methods outperform the highly sophisticated multiple input methods [34] and [35].

4.1.1.2 *Long- and medium-term load forecasting approaches*

To predict the energy demand long time ahead it is necessary to describe the end-user's appliances and so the change of their behaviour in detail. To be able to get accurate calculation results information about the loads connected to the grid like their age, used technology, the change in technology, extension of systems as well as in the private sector the size of houses, the change in customer behaviour and population dynamics are essential. Basically there are two model approaches for long- and medium-term load forecasting – End-use models and econometric models.

End-use models

The end-use approach needs extensive information on appliances like mentioned in the section before. Customer's showing similar behaviours are categorized into groups represented by load profiles. So an average profile is calculated to simplify the handling of the user data. This approach is very sensitive on the quantity of information of the energy demand characteristics and their quality. A benefit calculating LTLF by the use of End-use models is that only few historical data is needed. On the other hand a lot of information about customers and their behaviour is necessary to get accurate results.

Econometric models

Another approach for LTLF is econometric models combining the statistic and economic theory. They are based on the estimation of load as a function of the weather and other load influencing factors. The load prediction is calculated by building customer collectives of different sectors like commercial, industrial or residential ones and calculating their future load consumption as a function of weather, economical and other variables. Combinations of end-use- and econometric-models are also mentioned in [17] but they require a long history of load data as well as detailed information about the end-user-load-structure.

Combined LTLF-models

The two previous mentioned methods were implemented in combination [17]. This model is able to predict and model loads for $(y+1)$ (one year ahead) based on historical data from the last 25 to 30 years. The input data of the model is normalized to average weather conditions and is able to predict next year's peaks consumption as well as their probability distributions.

4.1.1.3 *Linear Regression*

The method of linear regression is the simplest and mostly wide used approach for load prediction. It can be implemented in a bivariate as well as in a multivariate way. By the use of qualitative environment variables deterministic influences like special days, weather and other external influences can be taken into account. Linear only means the linear character of the parameters but not the shape of response surface. Various implementations of the method of linear regression are possible like polynomial regression leading to curvilinear surfaces. Most linear regression models are based on a linear trend depending on the actual lag time step. This approach is not applicable on business events like recession and booming due to the trends monotony on the whole investigated interval. In the reviewed papers the influence of weather parameters like wind and mainly temperature are taken into account as piecewise linear functions implemented through 3rd ordered polynomials.

4.1.1.4 *Similar Day Approach*

This method uses historical data (if available) to estimate the future energy demand by looking for days with nearly the same characteristics in the past. Day-properties for identification of the similarity are the weather, the day of the week and the date. Implementing a trend, the data from a similar day in the past can be up-scaled to the desired forecast date. The accuracy of this approach can be optimized by looking for more than only one similar day in the historical data and joining them creating a linear combination of them.

4.1.1.5 *The Use of Fuzzy Logic in Load Prediction*

Fuzzy logic is able to describe human expressions in a logical way to be able to use them for calculations (e.g. very hot – hot – cold – very cold). According to [36] load forecasting can be done in a faster and more accurate way than it is possible using linear models. In this paper the load is described as a function depending on the time (weekday-weekend), temperature and the day- or week-ahead energy consumption. The realisation of a fuzzy logic model is based on the steps of identification and relationship quantifying. Most of the statistical approaches' accuracies are limited due to unusual climate changes or sudden changes in temperature. Fuzzy logic is not based on absolute values but on differences between them (high or low temperature) so fast changes can also be considered. Because of the fuzzy character of the load well developed implementations of this approach reach a good accuracy level and outperform most of the statistic theory based methods.

4.1.1.6 *Chaos Theory based Approach*

In [37] the author proposes a method based on the use of chaos theory combined with neural networks. It is based on the establishment of a multi-dimensional chaotic time series in phase space. Further on the neural network structure is determined by trial and error in the network optimisation process. The initially randomly set neural network

weighting factors are optimised by training the network with according data. This is done using training a training sample x^k and the corresponding output value y^k .

The input value of the resulting chaos theory based neural network is a phase point and the output value the prediction.

4.1.1.7 Neural Network

A method enabling the forecasting of dynamic load behaviour in the time horizon of 15 minutes in a resolution of approximately one minute is proposed in [38]. Based on the observed past N step load series of time step n , the M value forecast is calculated using multiple underlying neural networks controlled by an upper neural network controlling the weight of each networks solution. The weights Θ of the resulting neural network is chosen by minimizing the overall error.

In [35] outlines the data prerecession as indispensable to enable neural networks to do their work properly. The paper deals with load prediction based on weather ensembles coming to the conclusion that the prediction accuracy of the forecast can be improved by the use of weather ensembles.

4.1.1.8 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)-Based Approach

Principal component analysis is based on the reduction of the dimension of a multivariate data set to a set of orthogonal variables. These are linear combinations of the original variables. This method can be seen as a development of the approach where for every period of the day a separate model is built. The difference is that the number of different models is minimized by the exploitation of similar pattern in them. In paper [39] an approach for a univariate model is shown based on the data of n days and a vector of $s1$ intraday periods. By the use of day-of-the-week dummies and a quadratic trend a regression based solution of this problem is done. Cross validation in combination with the method of minimum least squares is used in the mentioned paper for optimization purposes. It can be speeded up by focusing the attention on principal components. The results have to be converted back from the space of principal components to the space of the input data. When weather data is available it could also be implemented by extending the model to a multivariate one.

4.1.1.9 Exponential Smoothing Method

There are numerous variants in implementing exponential smoothing mechanisms [40]. The simplest one is the **first order exponential smoothing** determining the $n^{\text{th}}+1$ step's estimate \tilde{y}_{n+1} by a λ weighted sum of the n^{th} step's estimate \tilde{y}_n and the n^{th} step's real value y_n .

$$\tilde{y}_{n+1} = \lambda \cdot y_n + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \tilde{y}_n$$

In general the formula can be rewritten as a recursive weighted sum in terms of \tilde{y}_n being the estimate and y_n the observed value at time step n .

$$a_n = \alpha \cdot y_n + (1 - \alpha) \cdot a_{n-1}$$

This first order approach can be extended to a **second order exponential smoothing** method taking a trend into account. A linear trend basically goes increasing or decreasing over the number of time steps.

$$\tilde{y}_{n+h} = a_n + h \cdot b_n$$

$$a_n = \alpha \cdot y_n + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (a_{n-1} + b_{n-1})$$

$$b_n = \beta \cdot y_n + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (a_n - a_{n-1}) + (1 - \beta) \cdot b_{n-1}$$

a_t again is the estimate of the observed time series' value at step t being the α -weighted sum of the actual step n observed value and the previous estimate for y (a_{n-1}) with an added trend of step $n-1$ (b_{n-1}). So to be able to predict h steps ahead the actual estimate a_n for y_n is linearly corrected by $h \cdot b_n$ to take the linear trend at step n into account.

Such methods are always trained using past values of the time series to predict. By evaluating the second-order exponential smoothing at the test data a forecast error can be determined by simply calculating the difference of the estimate and the observed value $\epsilon_n = y_t - \tilde{y}_t$. The sum of the squared forecast errors is then minimized and so the values for α and β are established.

The exponential smoothing is not limited to linear trends only but it can be extended to n^{th} -order exponential smoothing leading to a n^{th} polynomial behaviour instead of the linear.

A special case in exponential smoothing methods is the **Holt-Winters seasonal** exponential smoothing. Assuming a multiplicative model with a linear trend the time series y can be predicted as follows.

a_n again gives an estimate for the n^{th} step value and s_n denotes the n^{th} step seasonality, p is the period length. α , β and γ stand for the weighting factors being determined during the training ($\min(\sum FCE^2)$).

$$\tilde{y}_{n+h} = (a_n + h \cdot b_n) \cdot S_{n-p+h}$$

$$a_n = \alpha \cdot \frac{y_n}{S_{n-p}} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot (a_{n-1} + b_{n-1})$$

$$b_t = \beta \cdot \frac{a_n}{a_{n-1}} + (1 - \beta) \cdot b_{n-1}$$

$$S_n = \gamma \cdot \frac{y_t}{a_t} + (1 - \gamma) \cdot S_{n-p}$$

So the seasonality in step n S_n is the weighted sum of the actual seasonality calculated by division of the real value by the predicted one and the seasonality one period ago. The trend is determined by the β weighted sum of the current trend of sample $n-1$ to n and the trend one sample before. The seasonality free but trend afflicted estimate of y_n a_n consists of the α weighted sum of the actual observed value de-seasonalised by the seasonality one period before and the one step before season-freed estimate.

By adding the step n trend for a forecast distance of h time units to the trended estimate a_n the non-seasonal value for y_{n+h} can be determined. To take account of the seasonality this value is multiplied by the seasonality factor for also step $n+h$ and period p .

The main benefit of using the Holt-Winters seasonal smoothing method is that one or even more seasonalities [41] (day, week, month, year) can be modelled.

4.1.1.10 Intra-day Cycle (IC) Exponential Smoothing Models

IC models can be implemented restricted or unrestricted, but both of them are performing poorer than most other approaches. This model type is principally based on one cycle for every day in the lag time. So it is not possible to model any weekly seasonality. This problem can be solved by modelling various intra-day cycles for differently shaped load profiles per day type. In paper [42], different intra-day profiles were designed for Monday, Friday, Saturday and Sunday. The remaining days were modelled by one IC due to the similar profile of these days. The accuracy can be improved by including an autoregressive term to this approach.

4.1.1.11 Auto Regression Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA)

The ARIMA procedure is a popular method for building statistical models and models for time series for a forecasting purpose which was developed by Box and Jenkins. The underlying method of the ARIMA model is the ARMA algorithm. It consists of an AR part which is the autoregressive one and a MA moving average part. The AR model aggregates values from the past weighted by a factor – the parameter – and takes a shock into account as a normal distributed random function.

ARIMA models can be extended to SARIMA (seasonal ARIMA) models taking one or multiple seasonalities into account [42] [43] [41].

4.1.1.12 Hybrid Methods

Wavelet theory approaches are summarized in the term of hybrid models. The idea of them is always very similar. First of all the input data are transformed into different resolution spaces. Then the sub-input data are processed by forecasting methods like ARIMA separately. The results of the particular subsystems are combined by an inverse transformation. In [44] this is done by a lifting scheme.

Figure 6: Hybrid model consisting of ARIMA models and lifting schemes

The results in this paper show, that the LS-ARIMA-LS-1 method performs better than ARIMA model in the focus of a day-ahead (d-1) forecast and this one performs better than a back-propagation-network. In this case the lifting scheme acts as a pre-processor decomposing the input data into sub-series. The prediction on basis of this series is done by an ARIMA model, whose results are post-processed using an inverse lifting scheme.

4.1.1.13 Stationary Wavelet Transformation

A second approach to develop hybrid methods is the implementation of a trous algorithm [45]. First the input data is decomposed in different resolution levels followed by the calculation of the generated subsystems. The calculation results for the independent subsystems show different coefficients representing an approximation of the input data in the particular resolution level. Finally the subsystem's results are reconstructed stating the forecast values. This is done by combining the coefficients of the different base wavelets. The subsystems can be seen as independent chaotic time series. Caused by the influence of each subsystem the approaches implementing hybrid models –especially the SWT - perform well compared to naive methods.

4.1.1.14 Expert Systems

This approach is a heuristic (experience based) one which requires the expertise of a human being involved in the investigated process like a system operator. It must be possible to express the operator's knowledge in a way that programmers are able to implement it in software. In [32] mentioned already implemented expert system makes use of 11 different day profiles, weather data and load data of the previous 5 years. This developed method out-performed a conventional Box-Jenkins method in STLF. Another mentioned implementation in [32] of expert systems is a site independent set of rules, which was already tested on several different sites in the US. The parameterisation and rules were supposed without any site specific knowledge, but the forecast accuracy could be improved implementing site specific parameters. The investigation horizon of expert systems is limited by the horizon of the implemented expert rules.

4.1.1.15 Support Vector Machines

The technique of support vector machines (SVM) is closely related to the method of neural networks, where non-linear functions are searched to model complex dependencies of variables. In SVM the non-linear functions are converted by a so called kernel into a more dimensional space, where it is possible to express them in linear equations and boundaries. The challenge to find a proper architecture for a neural network is replaced using SVM by the need of the optimal matching kernel. Some SVM approaches were already implemented resulting in a better performance compared to an autoregressive method [32]. An award winning SVM realization was designed on the basis of daily forecasts on a prediction horizon of one month (STLF).

4.1.1.16 Prediction of the Forecast Error Variance

In paper [35] a method for predicting the forecast error variance is proposed based on the research work done in terms of weather ensemble prediction. Three methods have been investigated for comparison namely a naive approach taking in account the n value prediction error of all forgone n step ahead forecast errors for variance determination. The second method is an exponential smoothing method determining the past and the actual values weighted sum. The last method is connected to the accuracy of the weather forecast rescaling the variance of the neural net's forecast error by minimizing it using only a part of the post sample time series. Exponential smoothing turned out to perform best for short lags and the rescaled variance methods for long lags.

4.1.2 TSO Forecasting Requirements and Practices

4.1.2.1 Background

The main obstacle when forecasting load and its uncertainty in the context of TSO operation is that only the vertical grid load is observable. TSOs can observe the vertical grid node at interconnection points between their grid and underlying distribution grids. What makes the vertical grid node forecasting difficult is that it consists of several factors such as renewable energy in-feeds. Taking into account all factors, the vertical grid load can be defined for a time step t and grid node i as:

$$l_{t,i}^{vert} = l_{t,i} - P_{t,i}^{wind} - P_{t,i}^{solar} - P_{t,i}^{conv,sub},$$

where $l_{t,i}$ is the actual load (including losses in subordinate grids), which is unobservable. $P_{t,i}^{wind}$ is the wind power in-feed, $P_{t,i}^{solar}$ the solar power in-feed and $P_{t,i}^{conv}$ the in-feed of conventional power plants in subordinate (or underlying) grids. However, only the uncertainty of $P_{t,i}^{wind}$ and $P_{t,i}^{solar}$ is known, which already presupposes many additional information as stated in chapter 2. Fortunately, $P_{t,i}^{conv,sub}$ does not exist in all grids or at all grid nodes. Moreover, the influence of $P_{t,i}^{conv,sub}$ is not as intermittent as the in-feed of renewable energy sources. Within the project we will model $P_{t,i}^{conv,sub}$ as noise until further information becomes available. Hence, the remaining uncertainty is the uncertainty of $l_{t,i}$. Disregarding $P_{t,i}^{conv,sub}$, $l_{t,i}$ becomes observable when the TSO has perfect knowledge about $P_{t,i}^{wind}$ and $P_{t,i}^{solar}$. Unfortunately, this is not the case. Moreover, the current lack of data allows only to model $P_{t,i}^{wind}$ and $P_{t,i}^{solar}$ while making many assumptions as described in more detail in section 2.2.5. Thus, it was decided to model the uncertainty of $l_{t,i}$ with a parametric approach based on grid nodes where the factors $P_{t,i}^{wind}$, $P_{t,i}^{solar}$ and $P_{t,i}^{conv,sub}$ are negligible, and, in a second step, transfer the distributions to other grid nodes. It is important to understand that this procedure will only be applied until more information on renewables becomes available. Thereby, TSOs have to make an effort, if the regulatory framework does not influence the flow of information advantageously for TSOs. When this information is available, the load uncertainty at each grid node can be modelled separately with the proper parametric approach.

In order to model the dependence structure between the load forecast errors at different sites, the same approach as in section 2.2.4.2 is applied.

4.1.2.2 Current forecasting practices

In this chapter the methods used by TSOs whose data are evaluated in the following is described.

Typically, the input data for the forecasting process is the dataset of the reference day (see also section 4.1.3.1.1), as well as the reference day's last valid power plant schedules, the power plant schedule of the forecast day as well as the forecast day's power balance.

The reference day is selected depending on the type of day to be forecasted. Mainly there are two different possibilities in reference day selection. One approach uses the day before as a reference, the other one the day a week before. So for instance a weekend day is more similar to the day a week before than the day before but in terms of weekdays except Mondays and special days the day before gives a better reference.

Due to the fact that many power plants do not feed into the transmission grid their participation on the load flow of high voltage nodes has to be taken into account. Utilising in-feed distribution factors TSOs are able to weight the in-feed power and assigning it to the influenced nodes.

By the knowledge of the realised power plant in-feed it is possible to extract the vertical load of each node by subtracting the weighted nodal in-feed from the reference day dataset. However the realised power plant in-feed is not available for this purpose so the last valid forecast value set is used.

Again the in-feed distribution factors are utilised to determine the participation of each power plant in nodal load flow. The power plant schedule is weighted by these factors and added to the before extracted reference day load values.

The power balance of the TSO's grid area is calculated and the slack node compensates an eventually existing difference to the given balance.

4.1.3 Methodology

The methodology developed subsequently focuses on the description of load forecast uncertainties for pure load nodes. As discussed previously (cf. section 4.1.2.1) a challenge identified in the course of the project is that there are many nodes with generation infeed at subordinate levels. Whereas uncertainty distributions for the wind and solar infeed have been dealt with in section 2, the uncertainty distribution for other generation infeed (e.g. CHP) requires further analyses. The focus of the subsequent analysis then is on deriving a robust approach which may be applied to a broad variety of load nodes.

4.1.3.1 Load data used

4.1.3.1.1 Data base and data refinement

The forecast error (hereafter referred as fce) for transmission grid nodes of two TSOs – labeled TSO1 and TSO2 hereafter - were evaluated on the basis of hourly values available for each hour at minute 30. The determination of the forecast-uncertainty was done by the subtraction of the snapshot-data from the DACF-data. The data of TSO1 contained power plant nodes, load nodes as well as mixed type nodes. TSO2's nodal data contained mixed-type as well as load only nodes. Concerning mixed type nodes the obvious generation data was already set to zero in the time series.

4.1.3.1.2 Missing data handling

Due to measurement errors and measurement device failures there are time steps in the time series of the bus bar's power demand without valid data. Time series containing too much non valid data were removed from the very beginning. Furthermore time steps containing non valid data points were removed hereafter to enable the analysis of the data. It has turned out that a good value for the limit of maximum invalid values per bus bar-time-series to be 10% to get the most information from the data.

4.1.3.1.3 Detail of View

The data was delivered by the TSOs as one time series per bus bar for a whole year (2011) for the snapshot as well as for the DACF. Caused by the effect, that e.g. in one substation bus bar 1 was planned to be in operation, but during operation bus bar 2 was used, both bus bars' forecast errors reach 100%. This behavior is not caused by the load's volatility but by the operational management and the operational planning. To avoid this planning related uncertainty in time series the bus bars of one substation were merged to one time series representing the power demand of one node. When during a merge there was one or more involved time series containing too much non-valid values it was withdrawn for the reason to avoid the summation of valid and non-valid values resulting in a non-valid value.

4.1.3.1.4 Normalisation

To enable a comparison of the time series data among each other a suitable normalisation was looked for. To avoid zero as a reference as well as extreme values (maximum or minimum values) the mean as well as the minimum or maximum values were disregarded as a suitable reference. Instead the 95%-5% inter-quantile of the snapshot-time-series (hereafter referred to as iqps - Inter Quantile Power Spread) was found to be a good basis for normalisation, so extreme values of the top level and low level 5% were neglected.

4.1.3.1.5 Effects of Assumptions

After the bus bar merging procedure 84 nodal time series of the TSO1 and 101 of the TSO2 were available. With a focus on load only 8 nodes in the grid of TSO1 were identified. In the case of TSO2 the zero data stating the generation part of the time series were handled as invalid data. Due to this procedure nodal time series having a huge amount of infeed were neglected because of the relative quantity of non-valid values in time.

For nodal time series investigation a set of 28 TSO2-nodes consisting of 6190 valid time steps and a set of 8 TSO1-load-only-nodes consisting of 6613 valid time steps were used.

4.1.3.2 Nodal Forecast-Error-Distribution

4.1.3.2.1 Distribution characteristics of the active power forecast error

In Figure 7 the mean and standard error of the active power forecast error are visualized for the nodes of TSO1's grid area. The data are plotted against the 95-5%-inter quantile

power spread in active power. The standard deviation is increasing with an increase of the power spread except for the violet and red marked nodes representing two exceptional nodes in the TSO's area feeding the capital city whereas the other nodes supply mainly a mix of urban and rural customer areas. The mean values seem to be non-related to the inter quantile power spread.

Figure 8 shows the distribution parameters μ_{FCE} and σ_{FCE} for the grid area of TSO2. It's obvious, that the expected values of the forecast error time series tend to zero and do not show a dependency on the inter quantile power spread. The standard deviation of the time series increases with the inter quantile power spread almost linearly. Due to this relation the parameters σ and μ were weighted by the respective nodal inter quantile power spread.

Figure 7: Distribution parameters (TSO1)

Figure 8: Distribution parameters (TSO2)

The iqps weighted values μ_{FCE} and σ_{FCE} of the forecast error are shown in Figure 9 for both transmission systems.

The expected value can be assumed to be zero for almost all investigated nodes of TSO2.

According to the data listed in Table 2, the average standard deviation of TSO2's forecast error is 18% of the iqps. The data of TSO1 cannot be analyzed in detail since the country size caused a lack in "load only" nodes. According to Figure 7 and Figure 8, four TSO1 nodes (2, 3, 4, and 5) have σ_{FCE} values rather similar to those of the TSO2 grid area. The expected values of the forecast errors are different from zero for half of TSO1's nodes. But this information is difficult to exploit for describing future distributions due to a lack of causal relationships between the mean error and the other available nodal information. Hence the best guess would anyway be zero.

The identified standard deviations of forecast errors are rather high compared to values found in the literature - this is certainly partly due to the fact that rarely nodal values are analyzed in literature but mostly load values of an entire TSO. Nevertheless these rather high values indicate that the load forecasting process could probably be improved at least for some TSOs.

Figure 9 shows the distribution parameters for all grid nodes as a function of the nodal inter quantile power spread. The red data points originate from TSO1's nodal data, the blue ones from TSO2's.

Figure 9: Weighted distribution parameters (TSO1-red, TSO2-blue)

4.1.3.2.2 Distribution functions for the nodal forecast error

To find the optimal parametric distribution describing the nodal forecast error an initial visual classification on TSO1's and TSO2's nodal time series was performed. The normal distribution and the t-location-scale distribution turned out to be candidates to meet the time series' histograms best. If the t-location scale distribution has a shape parameter ν above 20 it can well be approximated by a normal distribution. Yet empirically the shape parameter is in the range of one to eight and so it does not reach 20. Yet the t-location-scale distribution is not considered further since there is no relation between the shape parameter ν , which has a big influence on the form of the distribution, and the iqps or any other available nodal property (Figure 10 based on the iqps). Therefore the following investigations focus on the normal distribution.

Figure 10: Scale parameter of the t-location scale distribution

4.1.3.2.3 Normal Distribution fit

The nodal histograms of both TSOs are visualized in Figure 11 and Figure 12. They show the time series' centered histograms calibrated by their estimated standard deviation to enable a shape comparison among each other and the also plotted standard-normal-distribution's histogram.

$$fce_{norm}(n) = \frac{fce(n) - \hat{\mu}_{fce}}{\hat{\sigma}_{fce}}$$

Figure 11: Histogram of TSO1's nodal forecast errors normalised according σ_{FCE}

In Figure 12 the normalized histograms of TSO2's grid area are visualized. The histograms of TSO1 (Figure 11) and those of TSO2 too show, that high uncertainties located outside of $2.5 \cdot \sigma_{FCE}$ are usually well approximated but in some few cases underestimated for both grid areas. The probability of forecast errors near zero is underestimated by the normal distribution. In the range between 2.5 and $1 \cdot \sigma_{FCE}$ the real nodes' forecast error distributions are almost in every case overestimated by the approximation. All in all the histograms of TSO2's nodal forecast error show a higher peak around zero compared to those of TSO1 in almost every node. This indicates that TSO2's load series prediction is more often correct but also has some rare outliers.

Figure 12: Histogram of TSO2's nodal forecast errors normalised according σ_{FCE}

Figure 11 and Figure 12 show that the nodal likelihood of the highly valued uncertainties is approximated well by the normal distribution whereas the probability of small forecast errors is underestimated. So the approximation leads to a higher probability of deviations of the predicted values and a lower one for exact predictions. This means that the normal distribution leads to a fit on the safe side. Given the number of nodes to be modeled in the ENTSO-E grid, the modeling of the nodal forecast error should be possible in a simple way. So non parametric distributions are nearly impossible to implement, due to the lack in dependence of available nodal information like maximal power demand, power infeed or power spread quantiles. Figure 13 summarizes the estimated normal distribution of forecast errors for the considered nodes, the corresponding statistics are given in Table 1 and Table 2.

Figure 13: Probability density functions of active power fce (TSO1-red, TSO2-blue)

Table 1: Normal distribution parameters of the active powers' DACF and forecast error (TSO1)

Node Name	DACF		Forecast Error		
	iqps	μ_{FCE}	iqps	μ_{FCE}	iqps
	in MW	in MW	in MW	in MW	in MW
1	171	-25.31	65.26	-14.80	38.16
2	340	-54.71	66.97	-16.09	19.70
3	261	11.74	55.79	4.50	21.38
4	220	7.60	39.18	3.45	17.81
5	138	7.06	28.80	5.12	20.87
6	159	-22.48	68.29	-14.14	42.95

Table 2: Normal distribution parameters of the active powers' DACF and forecast error (TSO2)

Node Name	DACF		Forecast Error		
	iqps	μ_{FCE}	σ_{FCE}	$\mu_{FCE}/iqps$	$\sigma_{FCE}/iqps$
	in MW	in MW	in MW	in %	in %
1	79	-0.86	13.95	-1.09	17.66
2	71	-1.21	10.30	-1.70	14.51
3	97	-1.45	13.73	-1.49	14.16
4	94	-3.18	25.26	-3.38	26.87
5	151	-3.20	19.76	-2.12	13.09
6	185	-4.83	27.07	-2.61	14.63
7	76	-1.71	12.15	-2.25	15.98
8	73	0.90	15.80	1.23	21.64
9	162	-2.58	27.35	-1.59	16.88
10	200	-3.03	28.71	-1.51	14.36
11	75	-1.63	8.54	-2.18	11.39
12	153	-1.02	26.83	-0.67	17.54
13	97	-1.53	18.15	-1.58	18.71
14	166	-1.66	29.25	-1.00	17.62
15	99	-1.12	22.33	-1.13	22.55
16	157	-7.91	38.62	-5.04	24.60
17	180	-4.20	24.44	-2.34	13.58
18	176	-2.91	24.47	-1.65	13.91
19	71	5.13	15.19	7.22	21.39
20	103	-4.89	17.12	-4.75	16.62
21	89	-0.55	19.31	-0.61	21.70
22	249	-4.01	73.94	-1.61	29.70

4.1.3.2.4 Test Statistics for Normality and T-Location-Scale Distribution

Table 3 and Table 4 show the results of the tests on normality and t-location-scale distribution. To test the time series on normality, the Jarque-Bera and the Kolmogorow-Smirnow tests were performed. The Jarque-Bera test identified the TSO1 node 5 to be the only data series being normally distributed. The Kolmogorow-Smirnow test rejected the null hypothesis on t-location-scale distribution as well as the null hypotheses on normality for all TSO2 nodes. Some of the nodes of TSO1 were identified to be t-location scale distributed, but a missing connection between the shape parameter of this parametric distribution and the given properties by the time series prevents its use.

Table 3: Load-nodes' time series test statistics (TSO1)

Node Name	Jarque-Bera test on normality		Kolmogorow- Smirnow test on normality		Kolmogorow- Smirnow test on t-locationscale	
	test result	test statistics	test result	test statistics	test result	test statistics
1	1	704.44	1	0.10	1	0.04
2	1	5301.19	1	0.05	1	0.03
3	1	1360.24	1	0.03	0	0.01
4	1	103.54	1	0.05	1	0.02
5	0	0.75	0	0.02	0	0.02
6	1	11594.91	1	0.11	0	0.02

The test-statistics of the Kolmogorow-Smirnow (KS) test is the maximal absolute deviation between the cumulative density function (cdf) of the time series and the cdf of a fitted normal distribution. So a smaller valued KS test statistic indicates a smaller deviation between the cdfs but does not allows a conclusion on the goodness of fit.

The Jarque-Bera (JB) test utilises the distribution's skewness and kurtosis to calculate the test statistics. A smaller test statistic value means a more normally distributed sample.

Table 4: Load-nodes' time series test statistics (TSO2)

Node Name	Jarque-Bera-Test on normality		Kolmogorow- Smirnow-test on normality		Kolmogorow- Smirnow-test on t-locationscale	
	test result	test statistics	test result	test statistics	test result	test statistics
1	1	945.72	1	0.05	1	0.03
2	1	378.67	1	0.07	1	0.03
3	1	608053.32	1	0.10	1	0.04
4	1	6310.84	1	0.16	1	0.04
5	1	491.49	1	0.06	1	0.03
6	1	1913.40	1	0.08	1	0.03
7	1	1499.30	1	0.07	1	0.04
8	1	22418.08	1	0.15	1	0.04
9	1	1815.87	1	0.09	1	0.02
10	1	3442.87	1	0.10	1	0.03
11	1	14828.49	1	0.10	1	0.04
12	1	2099.36	1	0.08	1	0.02
13	1	2425.54	1	0.07	1	0.03
14	1	1063.51	1	0.06	1	0.02
15	1	120.10	1	0.04	1	0.03
16	1	2936.07	1	0.14	1	0.04
17	1	441.64	1	0.06	1	0.03
18	1	4678.15	1	0.09	1	0.03
19	1	278.81	1	0.06	1	0.04
20	1	5428.51	1	0.09	1	0.03
21	1	1106.99	1	0.09	1	0.03

22 0 3.20 1 0.03 1 0.03

4.1.3.3 Correlation of forecast errors between nodes

Besides the distribution of the forecast errors for individual nodes also the correlation among errors for different nodes is important for the overall distribution. The corresponding correlations are analyzed in the subsequent sections.

4.1.3.3.1 TSO1

The correlation coefficients for each node with each other node are illustrated in Figure 14 for the active power forecast error for TSO1. In almost all cases there is no mentionable correlation coefficient for any of the nodes.

Figure 14: Nodal uncertainty correlation concerning the active power

4.1.3.3.2 TSO2

To identify correlated nodes a correlation coefficient matrix of the load-only nodes was determined and illustrated in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Nodal uncertainty correlation concerning the active power

In Figure 16 the correlation coefficient matrix of the nodal forecast uncertainties for nightly time values is shown. On the other hand, Figure 17 illustrates the correlation coefficient matrix for the day period.

Figure 16: Nodal forecast error correlation during nighttime

Figure 17: Nodal forecast error correlation during daytime

By visual comparison of those two figures it can be seen, that nodes correlating by day also show a correlation by night. So photovoltaic-power-generation can be excluded as a cause for this correlation. If PV would be the major source of the correlations by day there should not be a correlation of the same node groups' nightly values.

A general connection between the correlating nodes and underlying common grid parts could not be found. Different control groups are a possible reason for the existing

correlations due to a control group wide load and generator scaling to reach given exchange values.

4.1.3.4 Forecast Horizon Variance Dependency

It seems likely that a short prediction horizon results in more accurate forecasts than forecasts with a long time horizon due to the declining stability of the forecasted value caused by e.g. changes in weather.

Figure 18 leads to the conclusion that the mentioned effect does not exist for the evaluated nodes. The variance of the forecast error does not increase for longer forecast horizons - however nearly all nodes show a higher variance during the midday hours. Almost every node's variance shows a minimum in the early morning hours (0h-5h) and also smaller values the evening hours (20-24h).

Figure 18 Nodal variance over the forecast horizon

4.1.3.5 Error Propagation

An error propagation regarding a wrong guess for the load in the first hour seems to be likely due to the fact that most TSOs use load time series extracted from a reference day in the past for future load prediction. In Figure 19 and Figure 20 the correlation coefficients of the hourly time series (meaning one time series per hour leading to 24 time series each one value per day) in forecast errors are shown. The left figure shows visualized data for TSO1, the right one for TSO2. It's obvious that both correlation coefficient diagrams show a high correlation for the early morning hours indicating a similar forecast errors for the morning hours in both grids – this gives no indication on the magnitude of the forecast error but simply on its time correlation structure.

There is also a considerable correlation between the morning hours and the rest of the day. This leads to the conclusion that a forecast error present in the morning hours affects the accuracy of prediction for the whole day.

The right picture shows a node in the grid area of TSO2 with PV in-feed in the underlying grid area in contrast to the before mentioned node of TSO1. It can be seen that the high morning hour correlation is still present as well as the mentionable correlation between morning and evening hours. But in the case of nodes with large PV infeed the forecast error of the midday hours is hardly correlated with the morning hours and is only weakly correlated with the evening forecast errors.

Figure 19: Hourly forecast error correlation coefficients in the grid of TSO1

Figure 20: Hourly forecast error correlation coefficients in the grid of TSO2

4.2 Power plant outages

Although the quality and reliability of modern power and transmission systems in Europe is already very high, it is a great challenge for operators and designers to improve reliability constantly, especially with regard to the increasingly more important role of renewable

energy sources in the build-up of power systems. Nevertheless, the power supply to the customers is still primarily guaranteed by conventional generating plants which are undoubtedly qualified as the most reliable ones, and which already have demonstrated an economic operation working at high utilization.

However, a continuous availability of generating units should never be assumed due to a wide variety of possible system and component failures which cannot be ruled out completely. Generally, high availability and reliability is desirable and in a sense cost-saving, because every outage and the following repair tasks simply lead to a production and yield gap. On the other hand, an excessive investment in high quality components and system redundancies to increase reliability can cause a high economic inefficiency. For example, it is unlikely that a multiple redundancy of cost-intensive transformers at the connection to the transmission network will be economically worthwhile, if the gain of reliability is negligible. From this perspective one can see how much reliability and profitability are interacting.

Power plant outages cannot be predicted with certainty, so the issue at hand is an adequate description of the probabilities of outages.

Today, power plant designer and operators have access to a wide range of databases with historical system and component failure data, from which they are able to evaluate and optimize both the power plant structure and the operation, always including economic criteria. In addition, it is necessary to evaluate the amount of load balancing power, which essentially depends on the failure performance of the power plants in the network. At this, various reliability evaluation techniques for generating plants are taken into account. As modern generating plants can be understood as highly complex and integrated systems, many of those techniques require huge computational effort. As a consequence, this section illustrates basic evaluation techniques and points out a few ways for reducing the computations. Here, the main focus lies on the reliability evaluation in the operational phase of a power plant. Previously, a brief introduction to the characteristics of thermal power plants and their failure behavior is given.

4.2.1 Types of power plant outages

There are several types of power plants, starting with conventional steam power plants fired with coal, oil, gas or nuclear fuels, and ending up with gas turbine plants and combined gas and steam power plants. These plant types differ concerning their technical construction, their constituent parts and therefore also regarding their reliability, therefore a rough overview is given:

Steam power plants use the heat either from a coal/gas/oil-fired combustion process or from a nuclear reactor to generate steam which operates a steam turbine and generator. Additionally a condenser circuit is required for cooling. Generally, the working principle is based on a Rankine process.

Gas turbine plants derive their power from a combustion chamber using fast flowing gas to drive a turbine and generator. Here, the recirculating system follows a Brayton cycle [46].

Combined gas and steam power plants are able to generate steam using the heat from the exhaust of a gas turbine, so that both gas and steam turbine are operated. The combined-cycle-process principally allows a higher efficiency up to 60%, whereas the efficiency of power plants using single-cycle-processes is significantly lower [47].

Basically, modern generating plants consist of a large number of components and auxiliary systems. Gas turbine plants, however, take up a special role, because their performance is highly related to the behaviour of their main component, the gas turbine. Nevertheless, the remaining thermal power plants commonly possess similar auxiliary equipment and failure performances.

This is why they are combined in the following presentations and analysis. Some of the most important components installed in thermal power plants are:

- boilers
- turbines and generators
- pulverisers and drives
- compressors
- pumps (circulating water pumps, feed water pumps, condensate pumps, etc.)
- different fans

To guarantee a sufficiently high reliability, the complex and partly sensitive facilities of a power plant require periodic maintenance. This includes auditing measures as well as preventive replacements of stressed wearing parts. In order to operate the power plant under the most economic and efficient conditions, audit plans are created which normally set the maintenance in times of low load (probably during the summer months). Unavailabilities due to maintenance principally require a special consideration while analysing larger power systems combining many generating plants. In the evaluation of single power plants during the daily operation, which is the intention here, maintenance can be neglected.

Reasons for forced reductions of power supply, i.e. outages, can be various. Software and construction problems during the commissioning as well as age-related failures after economic lifetime (a behaviour described by the classic bathtub hazard function) are, however, not taken into account, as constant failure rates are assumed below for simplification [48].

At this point, there remains a diversity of failures and underperformances that are not negligible during the operational phase. In the following they are presented briefly.

4.2.1.1 Total failures

Total failures are by definition equal to a total loss of power output of a unit. Many models expect that the two states „up” and „down” describe the behaviour of generating plants adequately [49]. In fact, damages on components, which are placed in crucial parts of the energy conversion process, mostly result in a complete shut-down of the power plant. This can, for example, be related to turbines, generators or transformers, if they are not laid out in parallel structures (for example due to economic reasons).

Repair time, however, varies a lot and depends on factors like promptness of troubleshooting respecting the length of cooling down the boilers and dismantling, but also the time for procuring the spare parts (if necessary) [48]. Concerning reliability evaluation during the daily operation, it is possible to identify arguments for neglecting repair processes [50].

4.2.1.2 Partial Failures

It is not rare to see that failures of power plant components do not result in a total loss of power but in a reduced power output, in the literature described as a „derated state of a unit” [50]. This is due to the fact that modern power plants are consisting of many redundant structures and items assisting each other. In the field of coal-fired power plants failures of feed water pumps or pulverisers can be significant for partial reductions. Depending on the power plant design a loss of each, for example, could cause a 25% (if there are 4) or 33% (if there are 3) derating of the power output. Generally, reduction of power output can vary between quite small (1%) and great amounts (up to 50%). Power output reductions of more than 50% could automatically lead to a complete shut-down of the unit [51].

A summary of frequencies of outages and reductions as a result of partial and total failures in different power plant types, is given based on data from the German association VGB PowerTech in Table 5 [52].

Table 5: Failure frequencies according to [53]

Power plant types	Frequency total failures in 1/a	Frequency partial failures in 1/a	Average relative reduction during partial failures in %
Nuclear	1.1	1.2	27
Hard Coal	6.6	4.2	32
Lignite	4.5	1.7	37
Oil/gas	3.9	1.1	50
Gas and steam	12.1	7.3	32
Gas turbines	2.5	0.3	50

4.2.1.3 Electrical failures

Besides, electrical systems can be seen as a potential source of errors in generating plants, too. An electrical failure can have effect on various parts of the generating plant and can also lead to a complete shut-down of the unit. The more extensive the electrical auxiliary systems are, the more important is the evaluation of consequences of their failures. Generally, the consequences are quite difficult to assess due to the high

complexity of modern systems. In the past, various authors have been working on this subject [54] [53].

4.2.1.4 Other underperformances

Reasons for underperformances of generating plants, outside component and system failures, may be found in the quality of the applied fuels (5%) as well as in the existing temperatures. Especially in the field of gas turbines, the power output considerably depends on external temperatures causing variability up to 15%. But also for steam power plants high outside temperatures can limit, for example, the capability of the cooling towers and hence the power output.

4.2.1.5 Starting reliability

Another aspect of reliability can be pointed at in the field of quick-start plants, where especially gas turbine plants play a key role. Indices for the starting reliability of turbines, inasmuch as the data are publicly available, are quite important for the evaluation of the power plant system during the operational phase, as, to mention one aspect, one has to calculate the required reserve of quick-start facilities in the grid network. Today there can be assumed high reliabilities of more than 95% [55].

4.2.2 Reliability Evaluation

To determine power plant availability, diverse methods are available. In the following an overview on basic reliability evaluation techniques is given while concentrating on the state-enumeration-method, which is a simple but at the same time the most frequently used algorithm for evaluating power plant reliability [56]. It bases on the idea that a generating plant can take up a wide range of states, depending on the magnitude of failures, which can be determined by a state-by-state-procedure.

In the simplest form, one can assume two parallel generating units each containing both a boiler and a generator.

Figure 21: Typical station configuration

Assuming that every failure of at least one subsystem „boiler” or „generator” will result in an outage of the unit, it is possible to describe the probabilities of each state of power output on the basis of a state enumeration. Consider a subsystem-availability of 98% each and therefore a unit-availability of $0.98 \cdot 0.98 = 0.9604$ with a unit-capacity of 100 MW each, this simplified structure allows us to calculate the states of power output in 3 steps [50].

From this follows the expected output of the station:

$$E(\text{output}) = 200\text{MW} \cdot 0.9224 + 100\text{MW} \cdot 0.0760 = 192.08\text{MW}.$$

For a better overview, in the given example the states of the individual subsystems „boiler” and „generator” are already aggregated to the states of the units. In a general procedure without simplifications one has to list $2^4 = 16$ states, although, in this simple case, many result in the same output. As a consequence, one can easily imagine that the calculation using state-enumeration gets more complex, if the numbers of components increases, the component states are not reduced to the states on/off and the configuration structure is more branched. And needless to say, it is not enough to combine the main components of generating units in order to get realistic results of the power plant reliability as modern generating plants contain a high number of further components and auxiliary systems. In this connection, Endrenyi formulates a general procedure for describing the states of a generating system using state-enumeration-method, also including transition rates and thus failure frequencies and durations [56]. Indeed, also the 2^n -difficulty is pointed out and hence different approximations in order to reduce the enormous computational effort that is required for this kind of reliability evaluation are discussed. One of them deals with the simple idea of truncating the state space, which may contain both subsets working and failed component states. To put it simple, output states with many overlapping failures seem to be very rare and are, from some point of view, negligible in comparison with single-failures and, if added, double-failures. Thus this simplification can offer a huge save on computations. Other techniques, like the minimal-cut-method, do not seem to be always relevant for operational studies.

Billinton equally refers to the possibility of neglecting more than one failure and (or) the repair process at least during a lead time of the operational phase. Considering partial failures, he defines a simplified state space diagram of derated states, exemplarily shown in Figure 22 [50].

Figure 22: State space diagram during the operational phase

Assuming that s_i is the transition rate into state i and T the lead time, the probability P_i of operating in state i can be calculated very easily by $P_i = s_i T$ [57].

Nevertheless, this state space diagram will also grow rapidly and can become confusing, if an increasing number of components is included. For this reason one may reduce the model by combining component failures with similar consequences on the power output and by neglecting rare system states, so that a division in output states rather than component states and an aggregation of equivalent transition rates is required [57]. If one further assumes the possibility that one derated state can enter another, the diagram in Figure 23 will follow.

Figure 23: Modified state space diagram

To sum up, power plant reliability evaluation using state-enumeration and similar techniques is always connected with the question of computational effort. Reducing the generating plant systems reasonably to have both proportional effort and realistic results is a great challenge for plant designers and operators. In connection with the evaluation of power systems, a lot of papers were published in the past [58]. To list some techniques determining reliability indices aside the state-enumeration processes, Monte Carlo Simulations [59] and Population-based-Intelligent Search [57] [60] can be mentioned. Although relevant publications mostly refer to the evaluation of power systems combining many power plants, some of those methods generally can also be adapted for evaluating single generating plants.

Basically, the introduced techniques allow a statistical description (among others) of the output probabilities of generating plants. In order to achieve this, however, a wide range of component failure data and information of the exact power plant processes are required. Due to computational effort and a possible lack of data, huge simplifications have to be assumed.

4.2.3 Methodology

Following the previous considerations, power plant outages can be modeled using standard procedures based on state-enumeration. While a component-wise modeling of failures rapidly gets cumbersome, an aggregate description of the power plant availability and outages is possible. In a first step, a binary distribution (outage yes/no) is of sufficient accuracy to describe the possible events in the present context. Cascading effects

between different units within one site could be considered in an extended version. Also partial outages (reduced availabilities) could be modeled in an improved version yet are not of primordial importance in a first step.

For the failure probability, power plant statistics from VGB [55] and scientific work (e.g. [61]) can be used. They throughout indicate a very low probability of individual failures, yet for the entire power plant portfolio of a country, the probability becomes non-negligible.

5 Combination of uncertainties and provision of overall system states

This chapter is concerned with finding a suitable description of the aforementioned uncertainties in terms of integrating them into the operational process of TSOs and providing a consistent overall system state description. In other words, a suitable interface between the uncertainties and system states has to be identified. In the field of electrical engineering this is known as probabilistic load flow (PLF) calculation, although PLF requires the uncertainties of active and reactive injection as well as active and reactive load [62]. Because the uncertainty of reactive load is not considered in the WP2-part of the DOW [1], a Q-model is developed in the framework of task 2.4 and not finalized yet. However, preliminary results show that the current Q-forecast can be improved in terms of the accuracy with the new model, especially when the proper explanatory P-variables are taken into account. In addition, it provides the necessary uncertainties.

In order to simulate the P-uncertainties, the first step contains the modeling of the different uncertainties (wind and solar power as well as load) and their transformation into P-uncertainties for each grid node. This is achieved for the RES uncertainties by following the subsequent steps:

1. Generation of Gaussian distributed random variables,
2. Computation of the marginal distributions for the nodal values using a copula,
3. Transformation of the Gaussian marginals into the non-parametric conditional distributions,
4. Insertion of the condition (deterministic wind or solar power forecast)

and results in the (un-)conditional forecast error distribution and forecast error values, respectively. In case of load forecast uncertainty, step 3 and 4 are not necessary. Step 1 could be extended so that the correlations between load, solar and wind power are regarded. For the example of wind and solar power, it has been shown that there is a low negative correlation between the power outputs of the two [63]. However, how this is affecting the uncertainty has to be examined in a later step of the project.

Now, the specific uncertainties covering all intermittent production changes and demand side uncertainties can be used to estimate the intraday changes as outlined in chapter 3 and, thus, changes on the conventional generation side. Thereby, a few particularities, e.g. run-of-the-river hydro power plants, have to be incorporated.

Having the uncertainties of injections and load, a PLF can be implemented by applying either a numerical or an analytical approach [62]. The analytical approach assumes mostly totally independent or linear-correlated and normally distributed power variables, which makes it unsuitable for our purposes. The numerical approach, which is normally implemented as a Monte Carlo (MC) method, can deal with any input and without making any assumptions on the input. This is achieved by running many deterministic load flows, what allows for a usage of the regular load flow set-up and provides the most accurate results. Obviously, the disadvantage would be the rather long computation time. However, the MC method is applied to provide the TSO with a distribution of system states due to the aforementioned advantages.

It is worth mentioning that the copulas in combination with the MC approach guarantee that the spatial interdependences of uncertainties between different sites are modeled properly. The whole approach is summed up in Figure 24.

Out of scope of the deliverable at hand but of further interest is the forecasting of critical system states. Thereby, the here obtained distributions of system states and their interdependence with the analyzed uncertainties are a crucial input parameter. However, in order to provide critical system states in a limited amount of computation time, a more sophisticated process has to be developed than the time consuming “classical” MC method. This approach should consider and make use of additional information which is not used for the determination of the uncertainties.

Figure 24: Combination of uncertainties and provision of system states

6 Conclusions

The modeling of uncertainties for power systems is a complex task, which requires the consideration of many factors. Some elements of uncertainty like load forecast errors and power plant outages have been present for decades. Engineering rules have been developed to handle them in practice yet these rules are no longer sufficient when it comes to integrate larger fractions of renewables into the system.

Then the various uncertain factors have to be modeled in detail and their distribution characteristics have to be approximated as good as possible. Here the project has provided substantial input which will then be used to determine load flows and system states in a next step. This is then a key element for the identification of critical system states and the determination of adequate remedial measures.

By providing a general approach based on parameter estimations and Monte Carlo simulations, the work package 2 provides a framework that may be easily adapted in the future to changing circumstances or better data availability.

7 References

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